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Linguistic and cultural diversity in the classroom

Revista Letras Raras (RLR), a scholarly journal in the field of Linguistics and Literature, edited by the Laboratory of Studies on Linguistics, Literature, and Languages in Contemporaneity (Federal University of Campina Grande), is launching its second edition in 2022, along its eleventh year. Scholars and specialists in the studies of linguistic and cultural diversity have gathered seven papers on the subject, revealing the differences that exist within this domain of language/culture. Accordingly, the issue of **Linguistic and cultural diversity in the classroom** brings necessary discussions, exposing research results in different levels of studies, thus clearly marking how much it is a necessary subject for professionals on languages.

This issue has the collaboration of specialists from Brazilian and foreign institutions, professionals committed to the studies of linguistic and cultural diversity: PhD Prof. Bruno Rafael Costa Venâncio da Silva, from the Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Rio Grande do Norte (Natal, Brazil), PhD Prof. Margarita Isabel Asensio Pastor, from the University of Almería (Almería, Spain), and PhD Prof. Moisés Llopis i Alarcón, from the Pontifical Catholic University of Chile and the University of Chile. These scholars received several papers for evaluation, some of which were approved and others left along the way, though they represent an expressive number of researches that reveal this issue as a topic that needs more space for discussion.

In addition to the papers in the issue, this edition also presents four papers that fit the scope of the journal, going through Language and Literature. The authors come from several higher education institutions, such as: Federal University of Rio Grande (FURG), State University of Paraíba (UEPB), Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC), Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCEG), Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB), Federal University of Maranhão (UFMA), Federal University of Bahia (UFBA), State University of Bahia (UNEB), Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG), Federal University of Juiz de Fora (UFJF), Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ), State University of Southwest Bahia (UESB), Federal University of Pernambuco (UFPE), Federal Institute of Paraná (IFPR), Federal University of Pelotas (UFPEl), Federal University of Piauí (UFPI), State University of Piauí (UESPI), Federal University of Goiás (UFG), Federal

University of North Tocantins (UFNT), Federal University of Tocantins (UFT), Catholic University of Pelotas (UCPel), and State University of Mato Grosso (UNEMAT).

Once again, the esteemed reader will be able to read and share the papers from this issue of **Linguistic and cultural diversity in the classroom**, by also pointing the mobile camera at the journal's QR Code and choosing the text to be read. Let us, therefore, share knowledge because there is no meaning if it is not like this: sharing! Moreover, literary texts such as poems and short stories, in addition to an interview and an essay are here for you to read and share. Let us share language and literature! Let us resist and survive!

In the certainty of such an act, dear reader, we wish you a great reading!

PhD Prof. Josilene Pinheiro-Mariz (UFMG, Brazil)

PhD Prof. Maria Rennally Soares da Silva (UEPB, Brazil)

Editors of Revista Letras Raras: A Scholarly Journal of the Research Group LELLC – Laboratory of Studies on Linguistics, Literature, and Languages in Contemporaneity / Federal University of Campina Grande.

Translated by Rafael de Arruda Sobral.